

Supplementary Material 3

Conserved Tonneu Recruiting Motifs (TRM) motif alignment to four carrot gene amino acid sequences

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Two TRM conserved motifs were aligned to four previously uncharacterized predicted carrot genes DCAR_008585 ([LOC108208046](#)), DCAR_017186 ([LOC108220104](#)), DCAR_021448 ([LOC108228003](#)) and DCAR_027681 ([LOC108200088](#)). All genes are within the 1.5 LOD support interval of QTL peaks controlling length, width and length-to-width ratio in chromosomes 2,5,6 and 8.

We identified the M2 and M8 conserved TRM motifs of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) reported in Wu et al. (2018) in the previously uncharacterized carrot gene amino acid sequences.

Alignment of tomato TRMs conserved motifs to the carrot amino acid sequences was performed using MAST (Timothy et al. 1998) (<https://meme-suite.org/meme/doc/mast.html>).

MOTIF ID	Size	Sequence
1 M8 -	18	GQKPPSVVARLMGLDELP
2 M2 -	20	LEVVEVGLIEIEKELNDLIDE

PAIRWISE MOTIF CORRELATIONS:

MOTIF	1
2	0.13

No overly similar pairs (correlation > 0.60) found.

Columns whose match to the motif have a positive score are indicated by a plus sign. Loci where the sequence matches a motif are labeled in red.

DCAR_021448 (DCARv2_Chr6:22864332..22868406)
LENGTH = 940 COMBINED P-VALUE = 3.48e-09 E-VALUE = 1.4e-08

[M8]
GQKPPSVVARLMGLDELP
+ + + +++++++ ++

76
FSNGKKNGAR**RVDSGQKQGMKPTLV**ARLMGLDSLPAVQRNKSCKGYELGVDRGEEIATDSCALARQQ
IEVEKAG

[M8]
GQKPPSVVARLMGLDELP
++++ + ++

526
NGDVSFTTFSSSKNKERILAKPDDR**EYQSECTCTHSSQRSSAF**DTINRKRQTCFQKLPSPGDTLSVLEQ
KLKEL

DCAR_017186 (DCARv2_Chr5:12549833..12553892)
LENGTH = 942 COMBINED P-VALUE = 2.36e-06 E-VALUE = 9.4e-06

[M8]
9.6e-10
GQKPPSVVARLMGLDELP
+ ++++++++ ++

76
GTRNVDT**GQKYAMRTPTLVARLMGL**DSLPAVQRGKIKKISSDRIEVDTTGGKFASDCCQFGGQHKKFKPE
GSKHEL

DCAR_027681 (DACRv2_Chr8:20635645..20639639)
LENGTH = 780 COMBINED P-VALUE = 2.57e-03 E-VALUE = 0.01

[M8]
3.7e-07
GQKPPSVVARLMGLDELP
+++ +++++ +

1
METK**EQTPSVIARLMGFYETRH**QRPIHKKYRVLSEDYLRKSASIDLLLKSSCNGRSFRMSRVKMPEFKD
SFEGQ

DCAR_008585 (DCARv2_Chr2:43316019..43317136)
LENGTH = 340 COMBINED P-VALUE = 3.05e-02 E-VALUE = 0.12

[M2]
2.1e-05
LEVVEVGLEIEKELNDLIDE
+ ++++++ +

301 MER**GVKWNKFDEDEQELGLEIE**KQLLNCLVDEVLFDFDL

References

Wu S, Zhang B, Keyhaninejad N, Rodríguez GR, Kim HJ, Chakrabarti M, Illa-Berenguer E, Taitano NK, Gonzalo MJ, Díaz A, Pan Y, Leisner CP, Halterman D, Buell CR, Weng Y, Jansky SH, van Eck H, Willemsen J, Monforte AJ, Meulia T, van der Knaap E (2018) A common genetic mechanism underlies morphological diversity in fruits and other plant organs. *Nature Communications*. doi: 10.1038/s41467-018-07216-8

Timothy L. Bailey and Michael Gribskov (1998). "Combining evidence using p-values: application to sequence homology searches", *Bioinformatics*, 14(1):48-54.